

MANIFESTATION OF IMPROVISATION SKILLS IN THE TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL SKILLS

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Abstract. *This article talks about the competence of pedagogical improvisation, the importance of pedagogical improvisation in the educational system, ways to implement improvisation in the work of a future primary school teacher.*

Keywords: *elementary school, improvisation, pedagogical improvisation, character of improvisation, pedagogical communication, pedagogical creativity, creativity, criteria of improvisation.*

One of the main qualities of a modern teacher - his devotion to his profession, ideological conviction, love for his profession, and his boundless devotion to this profession distinguish him from other professions. Because the high level of education in the continuous education system depends only on the teacher and his professional training. One of the important requirements for a teacher is that he must have deep knowledge of the subjects he teaches. Deep knowledge of the subject and its theory increases his interest and raises the reputation of the teacher. Teachers not only appreciate the student's ability to convey this knowledge to children, but also appreciate his interest in this subject and his dedication. The high culture of the teacher, his deep knowledge will help him to successfully carry out educational work. A modern teacher should not only know national values, but should also be a firecracker propagator in the classroom among the wider community of parents. Pedagogical activity is creative in nature. It is known that creativity is needed only when a person faces a problem. Teaching activity has such characteristics. The main essence of pedagogical creativity is the purpose and experience of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical experience is rich in problematic situations. By advanced pedagogical experience, we understand the teacher's creative approach to his pedagogical task, searching for new, effective ways and tools in the education of students. Modern science and technology development requires the teacher to be creative, to be able to think freely about the important problems of science, to be able to convey the achievements of science to the student, and finally to teach the student to think creatively, do scientific research work, to carry out educative and innovative research. Therefore, the teacher must acquire research skills first of all. During the course of scientific research, the teacher collects and analyzes the works of great thinkers and scientists, draws conclusions based on them. He acquires very important qualities necessary for a modern teacher in the process of using science conclusions in his practical work. Pedagogical experience is the sum of knowledge and skills acquired by a teacher in the course of educational work. This is the teacher's pedagogical skill, which is the primary factor in the development of the science of pedagogy.

Pedagogical experience collection system:

1. Goal setting;
2. Analysis, generalization, conclusion;
3. Identifying achievements;
4. Collecting information.

The improvisational nature of pedagogical activity creates the necessary conditions to meet the teacher's moral and psychological needs for success, professional and personal growth, which is measured both by career growth and by rising to the highest level of skill and wisdom.

The modern trends of education development, the increase in professional requirements for the individual have increased the need to form the creative individuality of the teacher, to realize his creative abilities, and to develop the individual activity style. One of the components of creative activity is pedagogical improvisation. Experienced teachers have many techniques that can be used to solve various pedagogical problems during their career. But there are situations when the teacher needs to make quick decisions, be flexible in non-standard situations in the classroom and extracurricular activities. [1, 54]

What is improvisation? In dictionaries, the concept of improvisation is etymologically related to elements of surprise and surprise itself. In fact, this is a creative process, which is also its result. There are musical, dance or other improvisations. Teachers use pedagogical improvisation in their work. How to choose a way in situations that arise suddenly or unexpectedly, improvisation is born here and now. This is a stream of creative activity that is not interrupted by criticism, judgment or evaluation, that gives itself a form and direction, that flows "through" the author, that passes through him and finds time to observe the development of the theme and content.

Pedagogical improvisation (Latin *improvisus* - unexpected) is the teacher's ability to develop new solutions, as well as to quickly, flexibly and clearly respond to emerging pedagogical tasks.

All teachers use a certain scheme in their lessons. However, among them there are many who consider it appropriate to improvise - to deviate from the planned course of the lesson, to include in it unexpected, unprepared, sudden, here and now things.

In the process of improvisation (due to an unexpected situation), different actions are possible for teachers:

- **natural type:** effective improvisation actions do not cause psychological and emotional difficulties for the teacher;
- **stress-transformation type:** there is a mobilization of all the resources of the person to overcome the difficulties that have arisen;
- **a type of deliberate avoidance:** the teacher's conscious avoidance of eliminating an unexpected pedagogical situation ("not noticing");
- **involuntary braking type:** confusion and a full sense of the teacher's actions;
- **emotional disturbance:** the teacher is out of control, acts randomly, escalates conflict, cannot control himself or hide his feelings;
- **inadequate type:** the teacher hides his feelings, but cannot turn them into pedagogically appropriate experiences and actions.

According to L. Yu. Berikhonova's opinion, pedagogical improvisation is not an accidental phenomenon, but a natural, integral and very important component of the teacher's creative teaching activity, and works as an effective method of optimizing what is invented and a means of quick correction of the pedagogical plan in accordance with the pedagogical plan. [4,64]

Changed conditions of activity; in accordance with the main components of the educational process, pedagogical improvisation can be aimed at clarifying the goals of a particular lesson, the content of the educational material, methodological reception and communication.

According to V. N. Harkin, pedagogical improvisation is characterized by the following features [7, 264]:

- compatibility of creation and execution processes or their minimum gap;
- their immediacy;
- public character;
- the unity of logic, the concept of initial support.

The criteria of pedagogical improvisation can be distinguished.

1. Objective criteria

- suddenness (this is the surprise from the obstacle, the speed of response to an unexpected situation or a suddenly changed situation, the novelty of action, its unusualness and incompatibility with expected actions);

- immediately (immediateness of action);
- novelty (level of originality);
- openness (presence of audience, improvisation partners);
- pedagogical value (contribution to education, personality development).

2. Criteria for improvisation by the subject

- demonstration of thought work;
- spiritual and emotional growth;
- a sense of satisfaction.

3. Criteria of improvisation as perceived by the audience

- surprise (reaction to something unexpected);
- input;
- activity;
- emotional sensitivity;
- concentration;
- increase in interest;
- increase in tone and mood;
- depth of empathy.

Raised eyebrows, bright eyes, involuntary gestures, comments, laughter, etc. can be indicators.

In pedagogical improvisation, the components of the creative dominant are attention, imagination and inspiration.

Imagination is a mental process of creating new images, ideas, and thoughts based on existing ideas, knowledge, and experiences. Imagination is stimulated by the tasks facing a person, his needs, feelings, outlook, and the need for foresight. Imagination is characterized by the novelty level of created images, it can be recreational and creative. In the process of creative imagination, new and original images are created, often images of objects that do not exist now. Knowledge, feelings, experience, strong willed and intellectual actions, unconscious attitude, intuition of a person are involved in creative imagination.

The peculiarity of **pedagogical attention** is that it should be distributed to different objects (students, lesson content, etc.) at the same time and should be aimed at solving specific

pedagogical problems. Due to the distribution of attention, the teacher can "catch" changes in the educational situation and decide to change the action plan, that is, to improvise.

The presence of inspiration is of great importance for improvisation.

Inspiration is the highest state of elevation in which the cognitive and emotional spheres of a person are connected and directed to solving a creative problem. Inspiration is closely related to a sudden understanding of how to solve a task or problem.

The internal mechanism that activates pedagogical improvisation is intuition, and the main driving force is inconsistency between the original pedagogical idea and the new idea that appeared directly in the teaching or learning process, a more effective version of its implementation and a lesson project (cases, events, etc.) and object-subject conditions of its implementation. Pedagogical improvisation in the educational process can be aimed at organizing and clarifying educational communication, methodological techniques, content of educational material, education or educational goals.

As V. I. Zagvyazinsky noted, improvisation does not appear out of nowhere. Successful improvisation is possible only on a well-prepared ground. After all, it is not for nothing that they half-jokingly say that the best improvisation is a pre-prepared improvisation. The basis of successful improvisation is the experience of analyzing typical situations, knowledge of laws and trends, prediction based on reasonable hypothesis. "Creativity," noted V. A. Sukhomlinsky. - this in no way means that the pedagogical process is incomprehensible, only intuitive and unpredictable. Just the opposite. Precise foresight, learning the interdependence of many factors and laws of the pedagogical process allows a true master to change the plan in an instant". [9, 196].

There are different approaches to classifying improvisation.

According to the source of the event, pedagogical improvisation can be "natural", "unprovoked" (it serves as a means of implementing the pedagogical plan and operational adjustments to it) and "forced", "provoked" (it is a means of clarifying, the pedagogical project of the lesson in accordance with the creative capabilities of the teacher and the specific conditions of the activity).

According to the quality of the content, the level of novelty of the decision made, improvisation can be "standard", its implementation uses typical, standard methods of solving certain pedagogical situations, and can be "creative" in the process. The teacher identifies non-standard methods of influencing students or new combinations of already known methods.

According to the structure, the process can be

- Classic
- improvisation with homework
- Mixed or transitional improvisation (can be classical at first or homemade at first).

V.A. Kan-Kalik identified five options depending on the source of pedagogical improvisation in the classroom:

1. Indirectly induced improvisation (practical thinking and emotional stability play an important role);

2. "Inside" improvisation (depending on the individual creative characteristics of the teacher);

3. Improvisation arising from the logic of presenting the material (performed through the active participation of pedagogical thinking);

4. Improvisation based on introspection and class perception;
5. Improvisation limited to pedagogical discovery (result of "pedagogical insight").

V. N. Harkin emphasizes that pedagogical improvisation is a complex process that is carried out in four stages. [8,288]

Step 1 - insight. At this stage, an unexpected intuitive discovery of an idea, an original action, a paradoxical thought, etc. occur. Often, the concept appears in a non-standard situation or on the background of emotional upsurge.

Step 2 - intuitive and logical understanding the idea and choosing a way to implement it.

Stage 3 - mass implementation of the idea with intuitive and logical correction.

Step 4 - instantaneous intuitive-logical analysis of the result of improvisation. A decision is made to continue improvisation or reconstruction.

Improvisation should be taught to future teachers and young teachers with the help of a specially designed system of exercises, which are characterized by the purposeful reduction and gradual reduction of the time allocated for solving an unusual pedagogical task. Here it is necessary to talk about the teacher's readiness for improvisation.

V.A. Kan-Kalik determines readiness for improvisation by the presence of the following components:

- professional pedagogical component: the general content is determined by the teacher's professional qualification, consistency, dynamism, mobility of special knowledge and skills on the background of general high culture and knowledge level;

- individual-personal component: in some unusual situations of pedagogical communication with students, requires the mediating nature of the teacher's actions, prompt guidance and prompt adoption of pedagogically competent decisions;

- motivational and creative component: it is determined by the creative motives of the teacher, his passion for the content and progress of the educational process, the state of "working" creative inspiration. [2,78]

V.A. Zagvyazinsky defines the stages of formation of improvisational preparation of the teacher:

Stage 1 - includes the development of pedagogical improvisation skills aimed at organizing educational communication, i.e. quick identification of speech means of presenting the content of the educational material adequate for a specific act of pedagogical communication, conveying the content to the audience the ability to quickly determine methods of emotional, intonational and expressive delivery, organization of spontaneous communication.

2nd stage - improvement and development of pedagogical improvisation skills aimed at concretization of methodological techniques, including analysis of the methodological structure of the lesson, connecting the technique with the content of the educational material embodied by it, analysis of legality, using immediately determined methodological techniques

Stage 3 - formation of improvisational skills aimed at adapting the content of the educational material. The main focus is on the development of skills to connect the content of the educational material with the learning situation formed in the lesson. [9,45]

Thus, we briefly touched on the characteristics of pedagogical improvisation as a component of pedagogical creativity. Creative pedagogical activity cannot be fully implemented without the ability to implement and correct the pedagogical plan in time to the conditions of the

teacher's work, his own creative potential and well-being, the mood of the student body, that is, it is difficult to improvise without appropriation and the ability to justify pedagogically.

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